

White Paper on the Future of Digital Democracy

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Abstract

This paper explores the future of democracy by presenting four scenarios that show how digital society could look like in 2050. Using a realist science fiction methodology, the Scenario Development Technique from the UN Strategic Foresight Guide, and STEEP Analysis (**S**ocio-Cultural, **T**echnological, **E**conomic, **E**nvironmental, and **P**olitical), it presents four scenarios: representative digital authoritarianism, participatory digital authoritarianism, representative digital democracy, and participatory digital democracy. The paper is a visionary blueprint that allows readers to start reflecting on what future digital developments are desirable and undesirable.

Benefits

- To provide scenarios that for 2050 that allow reflection on how society could look like in 2050.
- To assess the positive and negative effects that contemporary digital trends could have.
- To establish a conceptual utopian benchmark that guides the ethical and technical development of the INNOVADE Digital Democracy App.
- To enable policymakers to move from reactive crisis management to proactive, trend-based democratic innovation.
- To enable policymakers to move from reactive crisis management to proactive democratic innovations and policies that support such innovations.

Why is it important?

This work is vital for bridging the “foresight gap” in digital policy. The future cannot be predicted, but realist science fiction allows us to start reflecting on what digital futures are desirable and undesirable, which in turn can guide human action in the here-and-now. It provides an intellectual framework for thinking about how society can resist digital authoritarianism and foster resilient digital democracies and a democratic public sphere.

Online resource

The White Paper on the Future of Digital Democracy is available for free online:
<https://zenodo.org/records/17747937>

Quote

“Digital authoritarianism challenges democracy as such. It is uncertain how society will look like in 2050 and if democracies will exist in 2050 or be superseded by new authoritarian or new fascist regimes. Digital technologies is embedded into the antagonism between digital democracy and digital authoritarianism. The White Paper on the Future of Digital Democracy outlines realist scenarios of how digital society could look like in 2050. It wants to stimulate the readers to think about what digital futures are desirable and undesirable, what kind of Internet we want, and in what kind of society we want to live”.

Prof. Christian Fuchs, leader of the Paderborn University–research team

Involved

Stakeholders

Researchers

Policymakers & policy-facing CSOs, Public Administration

Citizens & citizen-facing CSOs

